

Appendix B (Supplemental Figures)

Knowledge Graph-Powered Artificial Intelligence of Bacterial Metabolite Biosynthesis

Mathusan Gunabalasingam,¹ Norman R. Spencer,¹ Xi Xia Di,¹ Won Se Suh,¹ Tonya Malcolm,¹
Victor Blaga,¹ Nathan A. Magarvey^{1*}

Fig. S1. Curated monomers involved in the biosynthesis of specialized metabolites. The number in brackets next to each monomer type denotes the total number of compiled units, with several representative examples provided.

Fig. S2. Motif library expansion with amino acid derivatization. Sixteen reactions are applied to 336 amino acids, generating 10,889 unique BLOOM-DOS patterns. These reactions involve the calculation of individual starter, extension, and terminal units for various azole configurations. Abbreviations: KS (ketosynthase), KR (ketoreductase), DH (dehydratase), ER (enoylreductase), B1-B3 (beta-branching reactions), NRPS (non-ribosomal peptide synthetase), and PKS (polyketide synthetase).

Fig. S3. Motif library expansion with polyketide (PKS) derivatization. Twenty-three reactions are applied to 103 starter and extender units, yielding 1,571 unique BLOOM-DOS patterns. These reactions involve the calculation of individual starter, extension, and terminal units derived from five distinct intramolecular PKS cyclizations (e.g., pyran formations). Additionally, we examine backbone motifs present in PKS metabolites, such as polyethers (e.g., monensin) and spiral compounds (e.g., aspercitrininone). Abbreviations: KS (ketosynthase), KR (ketoreductase), DH (dehydratase), ER (enoylreductase), B1-B5 (beta-branching reactions, numbered one through five), TE (thioesterase).

Fig. S4. Atom tracking in Ascamycin biosynthesis. Mapping changes in atomic composition and state across individual reactions (denoted as R1, R2, etc.) establishes a framework for extracting core scaffolds from curated pathways within BLOOM-KG. The highlighted colors represent the specific reactions responsible for incorporating each atom into the metabolite. This illustration demonstrates how the Bloom-Atom-Tracker extracts motifs from mapped reactions and links them to the corresponding reactions and genes reported in literature (32).

Fig. S5. Motif library expansion with motif extraction from curated primary metabolic pathways using BLOOM-Atom-Tracker. The figure provides a breakdown of each pathway type, along with the corresponding number of derived units (in brackets) and example motifs. A total of 12,720 motifs are extracted.

Fig. S6. Motif library expansion with motif extraction from curated specialized metabolic pathways using BLOOM-Atom-Tracker. The figure presents a breakdown of each pathway type, along with the corresponding number of derived units (in brackets) and example motifs. In total, 4,194 motifs are extracted.

Fig. S7. Biosynthetic mapping of the type 1 polyketide (T1PKS) monensin using BLOOM-DOS. This example demonstrates the capability to map the T1PKS backbone, even in the presence of epoxide openings in polyethers (PE), due to the inclusion of motifs in the library that account for this specific chemistry. Annotated molecular regions are numbered and color-coded according to the provided legend. Abbreviations: MeMal (Methyl Malonyl-CoA), Mal (Malonyl-CoA), KS (Ketosynthase), KR (Ketoreductase), ER (Enoylreductase), TE (Thioesterase).

Fig. S8. Biosynthetic mapping of the type 1 polyketide (T1PKS) erythromycin using BLOOM-DOS. This example illustrates the precise mapping of small carbon precursor units in T1PKS biosynthesis, identifying the directionality relative to ester bonds. The BLOOM-DOS library incorporates flexible motifs (denoted with R groups) to account for post-assembly tailoring modifications, such as hydroxylation. The molecular regions are enumerated and color-coded according to the provided legend. Abbreviations: MeMal (Methyl Malonyl-CoA), KS (Ketosynthase), KR (Ketoreductase), ER (Enoylreductase), TE (Thioesterase).

Fig. S9. Biosynthetic mapping of the non-ribosomal peptide cyanopeptolin using BLOOM-DOS. This example demonstrates the accurate mapping of amino acids, with the library accounting for various amino acid modifications, including methylation, as well as rare modifications such as the conversion of proline to Ahp via the gene SpnB/C (33). The molecular regions are enumerated and color-coded according to the provided legend. Abbreviation: Ahp (3-amino-6-hydroxy-2-piperidone), MePhe (Methyl-Phenylalanine)

Fig. S10. Biosynthetic mapping of the non-ribosomal peptide surfactin using BLOOM-DOS. Despite the absence of a potential fatty acid starter unit, BLOOM-DOS provides an alternative biosynthetic route using type 1 polyketide units and reactions. The molecular regions are enumerated and color-coded according to the provided legend. Abbreviation: 7-Me-Oct (7-methyl-octanoic acid), Mal (Malonyl-CoA), KR (Ketoreductase), ER (Enoylreductase), TE (Thioesterase).

Fig. S11. Biosynthetic mapping of the type 2 polyketide (T2PKS) doxorubicin using BLOOM-DOS. The T2PKS scaffold S.904.52 is extracted from intermediate metabolites of rubidomycin biosynthesis with BLOOM-Atom-Tracker. This scaffold appears to be reused with different tailoring modifications in this example. The molecular regions are enumerated and color-coded according to the provided legend.

Fig. S12. Biosynthetic mapping of the aminoglycoside gentamicin using BLOOM-DOS. This example highlights the diversity of sugars within the library. The molecular regions are numbered and color-coded according to the legend.

Fig. S13. Biosynthetic mapping of the nucleoside nikkomycin using BLOOM-DOS. The nucleotide uracil is accurately identified, and S.1169.26 represents a ribose unit variation extracted from nikkomycin intermediates using BLOOM-Atom-Tracker. The molecular regions are numbered and color-coded according to the provided legend.

Fig. S14. Uncharacterized molecular motifs identified by BLOOM-DOS analysis of specialized metabolic pathways, organized by chemotype. Biosynthetic mapping of 46,807 metabolites reveals unmapped regions containing at least five atoms, which are grouped to identify recurring uncharacterized motifs. The reported numbers correspond to groups containing a minimum of five members. Abbreviation: T1PKS (Type 1 Polyketide), T2PKS (Type 2 Polyketide), NRPS (NonRibosomal Peptide), Ripp (Ribosomally synthesized and post-translationally modified peptides).

Fig. S15. Overview of the GAT-Graphormer Architecture. The network is represented by three key input matrices: a node feature matrix, an edge feature matrix, and an adjacency matrix (encoding graph connectivity). These matrices are initially processed by a Graph Attention Network (GAT), which performs message passing to update node features by aggregating information from neighboring nodes. The resulting node representations, enriched with local contextual information, are then further refined through a transformer block to capture global dependencies across the entire graph.

Fig. S16. Schematic representation of BLOOM-MOL Training. (A) The training process begins with a molecular graph representation, where nodes correspond to atoms and molecular motifs from BLOOM-DOS. The [CLS] node functions similarly to the [CLS] token in Transformer-based models for sequence processing, facilitating full-graph context representations. Edges correspond to the different relationships between nodes and bond features. All features are initially encoded as labels, which are subsequently transformed into vectors using an embedding lookup. (B) This graphical structure is converted into matrix inputs, including a node feature matrix, an edge feature matrix (incorporating edge types and bond features), and an adjacency matrix that encodes the connectivity between nodes. (C) During training, 15% of randomly selected units and their corresponding atoms from the molecule graph are masked, and the model is tasked with predicting their original labels. (D) The masked graph is transformed into matrices and processed by a Graphormer (Fig. S15). The updated

representations of the masked labels are then passed through classification heads to reconstruct their original identities. This self-supervised training approach generates molecular embeddings that capture biosynthetic features as annotated by BLOOM-DOS.

Fig. S17. Schematic outline of BLOOM-RXN Training. (Top) Reactions are modeled as homogeneous graphs, where all nodes represent atoms and all edges correspond to chemical bonds. Consistent with Fig. S16, atoms and bonds are represented as textual descriptors that capture their chemical properties. To differentiate between reactant and product nodes, a binary value is appended to the vector representations, which are derived from labels through embedding lookups. The first node in the graph is designated as the [CLS] node, providing a contextual representation of the entire reaction for downstream classification tasks. This graphical representation is then transformed into matrix inputs, including a node feature matrix

(encoding atomic identities and reactant/product designation), an edge feature matrix (capturing bond characteristics), and an adjacency matrix that encodes the connectivity between nodes. (Bottom): Two parallel downstream tasks were used to train the model for enzyme commission (EC) number prediction based on chemical reactions. The first task involved a standard classification approach, where the model predicted each of the first three EC levels. Due to insufficient data for the fourth EC level, a contrastive learning approach was implemented. In this framework, pairs of reactions were presented to the model. The squared Euclidean difference between the embedded representations of each reaction pair was computed and subsequently processed to determine whether the reactions shared a common fourth-level EC number.

Fig. S18. UMAP projections of reaction embeddings from BLOOM-RXN applied to reactions excluded from the training dataset. The reactions are color-coded by their first enzyme commission number. BLOOM-Rxn embeddings effectively encode chemical changes between reactants and products, allowing reactions with similar enzymatic mechanisms to group together. Examples of different reaction annotations are provided.

Fig. S19. Schematic outline of IBIS-ENZ and IBIS-DOM training. IBIS-ENZ and IBIS-DOM are both Transformer blocks fine-tuned from the UniRef100 pre-Trained protein BERT model from Elnaggar *et al.* (8) **Top Left:** IBIS-ENZ processes whole protein sequences to generate one residue (token) embedding per amino acid residue, and one [CLS] embedding per protein sequence (sentence). Embeddings are represented by rectangular bars containing inset squares, each colour-coded according to the model component from which it originates. Protein embeddings and residue embeddings are subsequently processed by linear feed-forward neural networks to perform the classification tasks outlined on the right. **Bottom Left:** IBIS-DOM generates protein sequence embeddings for biosynthetic domains based on the output of IBIS-ENZ. IBIS-ENZ residue embeddings are used to identify biosynthetic domains in protein sequences, which are sliced out and fed to the IBIS-DOM model. IBIS-DOM is trained to identify substrate specificity, substrate properties, and domain functionality using traditional sequence classification. Siamese contrastive learning was used in cases of very limited data points, wherein a model is fed three samples per step, optimizing embeddings to ensure that the distance between the reference sequence embedding (anchor) and a similar sequence (positive) is

less than that between the anchor and a functionally dissimilar sequence (negative). **Right:** A breakdown of the various datasets and training tasks for the complete training of IBIS-ENZ and IBIS-DOM. Colours along the right hand side of the image correspond with the appropriate embeddings, classification layers, and/or methods in the left panels.

Fig. S20. Schematic representation of IBIS-SM. (Top) Contiguous genomic regions are represented as a homogenous graph, with IBIS-ENZ embeddings representing open reading

frame (ORF)-encoded proteins, and weighted edges linking proteins encoded within $\pm 10,000$ nucleotides of one another. These graphs are converted into a node embedding matrix, edge feature matrix, and adjacency matrix for compatibility with the GAT-Graphormer (Fig S15). (Bottom) input features are processed by the graph attention network and Transformer layers to generate final node embeddings representing the metabolic context of each protein. Multilayer perceptron node classification heads are implemented in-line to predict whether each protein is part of a BGC, and its chemotype.

Fig. S21. Schematic representation of IBIS-BGC. (Top) For this model, BGCs are represented as heterogeneous graphs. The graph depicts unique node types indicated by the tensor (stacked box) colour, and unique edge types delineated by letters. This graph contains nodes representing chemotype labels from IBIS-SM, protein embeddings from IBIS-ENZ, and domain labels and embeddings from IBIS-DOM. A distinctive node corresponding to a BGC with a single label is introduced, serving as the representative embedding for the entire graph following processing with a Transformer block (depicted as n_3 here). Nodes with labels are encoded via embedding

lookups. Nodes with embeddings are reduced to the same dimensionality as label encodings using linear layers, and concatenated with the other node embeddings to create a node embedding feature matrix of uniform dimensionality. Adjacency matrices represent edge connectivity, while the edge type matrix specifies the edge type for each connected node pair. The edge matrix is processed to convert edge type labels into an edge feature matrix in a manner analogous to node labels (omitted for simplicity). These inputs are processed by the GAT-Graphormer to imbue the BGC embedding with information from all node and edge types, using the attention mechanisms of the GAT and Graphormer layers as described in Fig. S15 to generate a single embedded representation per BGC. (Bottom) The overall training principle used for IBIS-BGC. Embeddings representing two BGCs are generated as described above. The vector square difference is computed for these tensors and passed to five classification heads trained to bin the BGCs according to the Tanimoto score of the corresponding BGC compounds, ranging from zero to one in increments of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5, respectively. The right hand side indicates theoretical model predictions for two structurally-related molecules originating from different BGCs.

Fig. S22: Schematic overview of BLOOM-LNK training. (Top) A schematic representation of the BGC-Metabolite subgraph, illustrating the node types and relationships between molecular and genomic data. This structured information is derived from IBIS, BLOOM-RXN, and BLOOM-DOS. All nodes are assigned labels, except for *Pathway Reactions*, *Domains*, and *ORFs* (specifically, the proteins derived therefrom), which are embedded using IBIS and BLOOM-RXN to capture high-resolution patterns from the input data. Following the methodology of previous Graphormer training, this information is transformed into matrix representations, including a node feature matrix, an edge feature matrix (encoding different edge types), and an adjacency matrix that captures the connectivity between nodes. (Bottom) We construct subgraphs for pairwise combinations of known BGCs and metabolites within

BLOOM-KG. For each pair, we assign a Tanimoto similarity score by comparing the query molecule with the encoded molecule from the corresponding BGC. The model predicts whether the Tanimoto similarity score exceeds a predefined threshold (specified in brackets) as part of its training objective.

Fig. S23: Frequency at which the correct metabolite appears within the top five associations when comparing known BGCs against a metabolite database. Performance is benchmarked against PRISM and antiSMASH predictions, utilizing the median Tanimoto similarity score between predicted structures and query metabolites. BLOOM-LNK identifies correct relationships at a higher rate compared to rule-based approaches across diverse chemotypes.

Fig. S24: Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for rhabdopeptide (Compound 4 and 5) in *Xenorhabdus szentirmaii* DSM 16338. BGC predictions (top) are generated using IBIS, while structural rationalization is generated using BLOOM-DOS motifs (bottom). The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure, which are coloured according to molecular unit designation. See Appendix A for compound isolation and elucidation information.

Fig. S25: BLOOM-predicted BGC-Metabolite association for szentiamide (**3**) in *Xenorhabdus szentirmaii* strain DSM 16338. BGC predictions (top) are generated using IBIS, while structural rationalization is generated using BLOOM-DOS motifs (bottom). The predicted association is partially explained by aligning the enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure, which are coloured according to molecular unit designation. See Appendix A for compound isolation and elucidation information.

Fig. S26. BLOOM-predicted BGC-Metabolite association for xenobactin (**2**) in *Xenorhabdus szentirmaii* strain DSM 16338. BGC predictions (top) are generated using IBIS, while structural rationalization is generated using BLOOM-DOS motifs (bottom). The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure, which are coloured according to molecular unit designation. Adenylation domains with low predictive probabilities from IBIS are marked with a cross.

Fig. S27. Predicted BGC-metabolite association for xenoamicin in *Xenorhabdus innexi* DSM 16336 (first reported identification in strain) using BLOOM-LNK. The metabolite has been previously identified in *Xenorhabdus doucetiae* (34). The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation presented in Fig. S28. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation), TE (Thioesterase). Adenylation Domains: Ala (Alanine), bAla (β -alanine), Pro (proline), Val (Valine), Leu (Leucine), Ile (Isoleucine), Thr (Threonine).

Fig. S28. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative xenoamicin peak in microbial extracts of *Xenorhabdus innexi* DSM 16336 cultured under MM3 media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S29: Predicted BGC-metabolite association for kolossin B in *Photorhabdus luminescens* DSM 33568 (first reported identification in strain) using BLOOM-LNK. The metabolite has been previously identified in *Photorhabdus luminescens subsp. laumondii* TTO1 (=DSM 15139) (36). The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation presented in Fig. S30. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation), TE (Thioesterase). Adenylation Domains: Thr (Threonine), Val (Valine), Leu (Leucine).

Fig. S30. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative kolossin B peak in microbial extracts of *Photorhabdus luminescens* DSM 33568 cultured under MM3 media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S31. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for luminmycin D in *Photorhabdus luminescens* DSM 33568 (first reported identification in strain) using BLOOM-LNK. The metabolite has been previously identified in *Photorhabdus asymbiotica* ATCC 43949 (37). The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. IBIS occasionally misidentifies DH domains as PS domains based on sequence homology and very similar function, thereby implicating a potential association with Mal-DH in the metabolite structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation presented in Fig. S32. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation), TE (Thioesterase), KS (Ketosynthase), PS (Pyran Synthase), KR (Ketoreductase). Adenylation Domains: Lys (Lysine), Ala (Alanine), Thr (Threonine). Acyltransferase Domains: Mal (Malonyl-CoA).

Fig. S32. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative luminmycin D peak in microbial extracts of *Photorhabdus luminescens* DSM 105531 cultured under KE media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S33: Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for syringolin E in *Pseudomonas syringae* DSM 10604 (first reported identification in strain) using BLOOM-LNK. The metabolite has been previously identified in *Pseudomonas syringae* DSM 1241 (38). The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning the enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. IBIS occasionally misidentifies DH domains as PS domains based on sequence homology and very similar function, thereby implicating a potential association with Mal-DH in the metabolite structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation and numerous detected analogs presented in Fig. S34. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation), TE (Thioesterase), KS (Ketosynthase), PS (Pyran Synthase), KR (Ketoreductase). Adenylation Domains: Val (Valine), Lys (Lysine). Acyltransferase Domains: Mal (Malonyl-CoA).

Fig. S34. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative syringolin E peak in microbial extracts of *Pseudomonas syringae* DSM 10604 cultured under Nutrient media conditions. (Top) Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35). (Bottom) Additional analogs are identified under different media conditions based on mass matching.

Fig. S35. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for albachelin in *Anycolatopsis keratiniphila* DSM 44409 (first reported identification in strain) using BLOOM-LNK. The metabolite has been previously identified in *Anycolatopsis alba* DSM 44262 (39). The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation presented in Fig. S36. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation). Adenylation Domains: Orn (Ornithine), Ser (Serine), OH- (Hydroxy Ornithine).

Fig. S36. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative albachelin peak in microbial extracts of *Anycolatopsis keratiniphila* DSM 44409 cultured under KE media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S37. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for lysobactin in *Lysobacter enzymogenes* DSM 2043 (first reported identification in strain) using BLOOM-LNK. The metabolite has been previously identified in *Lysobacter sp.* ATCC 53042 (40). The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning the enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation presented in Fig. S38. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation), TE (Thioesterase). Adenylation Domains: Leu (Leucine), Arg (Arginine), Ile (Isoleucine), Thr (Threonine), Gly (Glycine), Asn (Asparagine), Ser (Serine), Phe (Phenylalanine).

Fig. S38. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative lysobactin peak in microbial extracts of *Lysobacter enzymogenes* DSM 2043 cultured under R2A media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S39. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for stendomycin (novel association not in training dataset) in *Streptomyces hygroscopicus* ATCC 53653. The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation presented in Fig. S40. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation), NMT (N-methyltransferase), TE (Thioesterase). Adenylation Domains: Thr (Threonine), Gly (Glycine), Val (Valine), Ile (Isoleucine), Ala (Alanine).

Fig. S40. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative stendomycin peak in microbial extracts of *Streptomyces hygroscopicus* ATCC 53653 cultured under GYM media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S41. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for laterocidin (novel association not in training dataset) in *Brevibacillus laterosporus* DSM 25. The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation in Fig. S42. Abbreviations: C (Condensation), T (Thiolation), TE (Thioesterase). Adenylation Domains: Pro (Proline), Phe (Phenylalanine), Asn (Asparagine), Asp (Aspartic Acid), Val (Valine), Orn (Ornithine), Leu (Leucine).

Fig. S42. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative laterocidin peak in microbial extracts of *Brevibacillus laterosporus* DSM 25 cultured under Nutrient media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S43. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for foroxymithine (novel association not in training dataset) in *Actinosynnema mirum* DSM 43827. The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure. This metabolite is also identified in the expressed metabolome, with annotated mass spectrometry fragmentation in Fig. S44.

Fig. S44. Experimental ESI-MS/MS spectrum of a putative foroxymithine peak in microbial extracts of *Actinosynnema mirum* DSM 43827 cultured under Nutrient media conditions. Fragmentation spectra are annotated using CFM-ID (35).

Fig. S45. Frequency at which the correct BGC ranks within the top five associations when comparing all BGCs in a genome to a known metabolite produced by the microbe. Performance is benchmarked against PRISM and antiSMASH predictions, using the median Tanimoto similarity score between predicted structures and query metabolites (13, 14). BLOOM-LNK identifies correct relationships at a higher rate compared to rule-based approaches across diverse chemotypes.

Fig. S46. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for nitrorepeptin (compound 1) in *Pseudomonas nitroreducens* strain DSM 14399. BGC predictions (top) are generated using IBIS, while structural rationalization is generated using BLOOM-DOS motifs (bottom). The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure, which are coloured according to molecular unit designation. See Appendix A for compound isolation and elucidation information.

Fig. S47. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for kailuin G (novel association) in *Photobacterium halotolerans* DSM 18316. The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure.

Fig. S48. Predicted BGC-Metabolite association for gageostatin C (novel association) in *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* UASWS BA1 (NCBI taxonomy id 1384051, genome accession GCA_000469015). The BGC is annotated using IBIS, and biosynthetic predictions of the molecule are generated with BLOOM-DOS. The predicted association is rationalized by aligning enumerated substrates from the BGC with the molecular structure.

Fig. S49. Unsupervised associations identified between BLOOM-DOS motifs and genes, observed in the known BGC-metabolite dataset. Graphormers encode the contextual relationships between ORFs and molecular units as numerical representations. Density-based clustering reveals distinct ORF and unit groupings, followed by a chi-square test to identify statistically significant associations. (Top) Novel Unit-ORF association counts with respect to each chemotype. (Bottom) Several of these associations align with findings reported in the literature, with examples presented in Fig. S52–S56.

Amipurimycin BGC

Predicted connection between S.659087.78 and Amc15

Amipurimycin

Fig. S50. Example predicted Unit-ORF association ($p < 0.001$) from the Amipurimycin BGC, supported by literature reported reaction (41). The top panel displays the IBIS-annotated BGC, while the bottom panel shows the corresponding molecular annotation using BLOOM-DOS.

Prodigiosin BGC

Predicted connection between S.1399.6 and PigM

Prodigiosin

— S.1399.6
— S.576.22

Fig. S51. Example predicted Unit-ORF association ($p < 0.001$) in Prodigiosin BGC, supported by literature reported reaction (42). The top panel displays the IBIS-annotated BGC, while the bottom panel shows the corresponding molecular annotation using BLOOM-DOS.

Dehydrophos BGC

Predicted connection between S.752.23 and DhpF

Dehydrophos

- Methyl
- Glycine
- S.752.23
- S.752.21

Fig. S52. Example predicted Unit-ORF association ($p < 0.001$) in Dehydrophos BGC, supported by literature reported reaction (43). The top panel displays the IBIS-annotated BGC, while the bottom panel shows the corresponding molecular annotation using BLOOM-DOS.

Saquayamycin BGC

Predicted Connection between S.1736.9 and SqnC

Saquayamycin

Fig. S53. Example predicted Unit-ORF association ($p < 0.001$) in Saquayamycin BGC, supported by literature reported reaction (44). The top panel displays the IBIS-annotated BGC, while the bottom panel shows the corresponding molecular annotation using BLOOM-DOS.

Violacein BGC

Predicted connection between S.1918.7 and VioB

Violacein

Fig. S54. Example predicted Unit-ORF association ($p < 0.001$) in Violacein BGC, supported by literature reported reaction (45). . The top panel displays the IBIS-annotated BGC, while the bottom panel shows the corresponding molecular annotation using BLOOM-DOS.

Fig. S55 Structure of novel compound nitrorepeptin (**1**).

Fig. S56 Structure of ESI-MS fragmentations of nitrorepeptin (**1**).

Fig. S57 MS/MS spectrum of nitrorepeptin (1).

Fig. S58 ^1H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO-d_6 of nitrorepeptin (1)

Fig. S59 ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ of nitrorepeptin (**1**).

Fig. S60 Key COSY, NOESY, and HMBC correlations of nitrorepeptin (**1**).

Fig. S61 ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of nitrorepeptin (**1**)

Fig. S62 HMBC NMR spectrum in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ of nitrorepeptin (**1**)

Fig. S63 NOESY NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of nitrorepeptin (**1**)

Fig. S64. HSQC NMR spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of nitrorepeptin (**1**).

Fig. S65. HR-ESI-MS spectrum for xenobactin (2)

Fig. S66 Structure of known compound xenobactin (2).

Fig. S67 Key COSY and HMBC correlations of xenobactin (**2**).

Fig. S68 ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ of xenobactin (**2**)

Fig. S69 ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO-d_6 of xenobactin (2)

Fig. S70. ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO-d_6 of xenobactin (2)

Fig. S71. HSQC spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of xenobactin (**2**)

Fig. S72. HMBC spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of xenobactin (**2**)

Fig. S73 Structure of known compound szentiamide (3).

Fig. S74 HR-ESI-MS spectrum for szentiamide (3)

Fig. S75 Key COSY and HMBC correlations of szentiamide (**3**).

Fig. S76 ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ of szentiamide (**3**)

Fig. S77 ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO-d_6 of szentiamide (**3**)

Fig. S78 ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO-d_6 of szentiamide (**3**)

Fig. S79. HSQC spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of szentiamide (3)

Fig. S80. HMBC spectrum in DMSO- d_6 of szentiamide (3)

Compound	R ₁	R ₂
4	H	Methyl
5	Methyl	Methyl

Fig. S81. Rhabdopeptide derivatives (compound 4 & 5) isolated from *Xenorhabus szentirmai* strain DSM 16338

Fig. S82 HR-ESI-MS spectrum for compound 4

Fig. S83 MS/MS fragmentation pattern for compound 4

Fig. S84 Key COSY and HMBC correlations observed for compound 4

Fig. S85 ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ of compound 4

Fig. S86. HMBC spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of compound 4

Fig. S87 ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum in DMSO-d_6 of compound **4**

Fig. S88 ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO-d_6 of compound **4**.

Fig. S89. HSQC spectrum in DMSO-d₆ of compound **4**

Fig. S90. HR-ESI-MS spectrum for compound 5

Fig. S91. MS/MS fragmentation pattern for compound 5

Fig. S92. ¹H NMR spectrum (700 MHz) in DMSO-d₆ of compound 5

WS-20-04.11.fid

Fig. S93 ^{13}C NMR spectrum (175 MHz) in DMSO-d_6 of compound **5**